

Geochemistry of hydric soils in Majuli river island, Assam, India

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Abstract : The wetlands of Majuli islands were studied to evaluate the development of soil indicators related to seasonal saturation and the processes affecting the rate of transformation of Fe and Mn contents across wetland boundaries. The elemental composition in relation to morphology and particle size of four representative hydric soils such as Kamalabari (P1) on active floodplains, Adielengi (P2) on swamps, Sonaribari (P3) on channel bars and Boritika (P4) on old floodplains were studied by developing colour indices and element to clay ratio method. The relation of colour indices with total Fe and Mn showed a significant positive relation between hue index and Fe ($r=0.43^*$)/Mn contents ($r=0.42^*$) whereas negatively related with chroma index. Similarly the total Fe had a significant positive relation with clay (0.63^{**}) and organic carbon (0.63^{**}). The distribution of Ca in Kamalabari soil (P1, weighted mean of 2.91 g/kg) and in Sonaribari (P3, 9.32 g/kg) indicated the rapid weathering and leaching whereas low Fe (less than 10 kg/m²) and Mn (less than 0.1 kg/m²) contents are due to loss through ground water flow. The Adielengi soil on swamps (P2) showed net gain of 25% for K and 136% of Cu with slight loss of Ca (28%), Fe (19.4%), Mn (13.5%) and Zn (17.4%) whereas severe loss of K, Zn and Ca in intensively paddy cultivated soils. An average linkage method was employed to workout chemical affinity and variability of soil properties among clusters. The cluster data showed that clay and bulk density are least variable whereas K, Ca, Fe and Mn is highly variable among clusters indicating the usefulness of these elements in hydric soil boundaries across landscapes of floodplain wetlands in the river island.

Keywords : Geochemistry, Majuli river island, hydric soils, element to clay ratio.

Introduction

A comprehensive characterization of alluvium derived soils in Majuli river island were made on 1 : 50000 scale and reported the occurrence of hydric soils¹. The morphology and physico-chemical characteristics of wide spread aquepts and fluvents in Brahmaputra valley were reported²⁻⁴. These soils have stratified textures, abundance of free carbonates and high organic carbon in surface layers⁵. Soil colour was used as an indicator of redox processes⁶ but often misleading because of parent materials⁷ or organic carbon or oxide coatings⁸, relict redoximorphic features⁹ and elemental translocations under acid environments¹⁰. These soils have variable groundwater influence and wide spread stratification of parent material. These soils reflect the translocation processes of soil solid and liquid phase¹¹, a ratio method (volumetric approach) considering element to clay was employed to workout losses and gains^{12,13}. Although, the nature of parent material influence on elemental composition¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

The exact role of pedogenesis in controlling potential nutrient reserves in relation to landscapes is not clearly understood. Similarly little information is available about elemental associations with redoximorphic features and particle size distribution. Hence, the present investigation was therefore undertaken with the objective of examining the relation of elemental composition of hydric soils in relation to morphology and particle size distribution and application of ratio method for calculating losses and gains of elements in Majuli river island.

Materials and methods :

Study area and soil profiles : The Majuli island (93°30'–94°35' E and 26°50' and 27°10' N) is situated in north of Jorhat district. The elevation on the island varies from 60 to 85 m above mean sea level. The island is bounded by three important rivers viz. Kherkutia Suti, the Subansiri in the north and the Brahmaputra river in the south. Four representative profiles such as Kamalabari on active floodplains (P1), Adielengi on swamps (P2),

Sonaribari on channel bars (P3) and Boritika on old floodplains (P4) were chosen for geochemical interpretations of hydric soils in the present study. Horizon wise soil samples were collected for these selected soil series for laboratory analysis. Particle size distribution (International pipette method), pH (1 : 2 soil water ratio), organic carbon (wet oxidation method), exchangeable bases extracted from in 1 N neutral NH_4OAc by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer model), CEC by distillation method and total elements in triacid digestion^{17,18}.

Colour index : The munsell colour notation was converted to a single numerical colour index as per the scheme of Evans and Franzmeier⁶. The scheme consists of three steps (1) condense the munsell notations of soil colour into a single number, (2) apply that number to the various parts of features of a soil horizon to obtain a number of that horizon and (3) integrate horizon values into a single number to represent the pedon.

$$C1 = (i=1^m \sum X \text{ matrix}, i \text{ C matrix}, i) + (i=1^n \sum X \text{ mottles}, i \text{ C mottles}, i)$$

$$C2 = [i=1^m \sum X \text{ matrix}, i (45-H \text{ matrix}, I + C \text{ matrix}, i)] + [i=1^n \sum X \text{ mottles}, i (20(45-H \text{ mottle} + C \text{ mottle}, i)]$$

where X = abundance (fraction), C = munsell chroma, m = total number of matrix colors, n = total number of redox concentration and depletion colors described, H is function of munsell hue rated as : 10R = 10, 2.5YR = 12.5, 5YR = 15.....2.5Y = 22.5, 5Y = 25..... and 5BG = 45, abundance assigned values (few = 0.01, common = 0.11, many = 0.35).

Mass balance using ratio method : The ratio method based on volumetric approach was employed (Fine earth) to calculate masses of pedogenic Fe, Mn, K, Ca, and P and clay for a ground surface of 1 m² down to the upper boundary of the C horizon or any arbitrary depth (1 m)¹². Relative losses and gains of the element under consideration can be achieved by comparing the element clay ratio in a pedon (=P ratio) with the element : clay ratio of parent material (=C ratio).

$$P \text{ ratio} = \frac{\text{Element mass in the fine earth of a pedon (kg/m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Clay mass in the fine earth of a pedon (kg/m}^2\text{)}}$$

$$C \text{ ratio} = \frac{\text{Element mass in the fine earth of C horizon (kg/m}^2\text{)}}{\text{Clay mass in the fine earth of a C horizon (kg/m}^2\text{)}}$$

The relative changes between soil and parent material was calculated as follows :

$$\text{Relative change (\%)} = \frac{P \text{ ratio} - C \text{ ratio}}{C \text{ ratio}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

Soil morphology and colour index values : Four hydric soils on four distinct fluvial land forms displayed horizon sequences of Ap-AC-C in Kamalabari (P1) on active floodplains with dark grey loamy textural sequence but have Ap-Bw-BC-C sequence in Adielengi (P2) on swamps with grey to dark grey silt loam to silty clay loam textures, Ap-B/A-Bw-BC sequence in Sonaribari (P3) on channel fills with olive grey (5Y5/2) to dark grey to dark greyish brown B horizons with silt loam textures and yellowish brown mottles and Ap-C1-2Bw1-2Bw2-C2 sequence in Boritika (P4) with dark grey to grey silty clay loam to sand textures. The hydric soils in Majuli island have displayed stripped zones or horizons of Fe, Mn due to reduced soluble forms under anaerobic conditions. The formulae of colour indexes as proposed to relate soil wetness and aeration characteristics by Evans and Franzmeier⁶ was used to calculate hue (C1) and chroma (C2) indices (Table 1). The data shows that the dark grey to dark reddish brown Kamalabari soils (P1) on active floodplains have decreasing trends of hue index (0.35 to 0.11) with little changes in chroma index (9.1 to 9.5). This soil has loamy with chroma 2 or less without any redox depletions. The grey Adielengi soil on swamps (P2) have low hue index (0.11) in upper 34 cm but increased to 0.55 in brown B horizons. This soil has sandy gleyed matrix in C horizons and chroma 1 or 2. This soil has low chroma index with little changes (2.3 to 2.97). The Sonaribari soil (P3) on channel fills have stratified textures with olive grey to dark greyish brown matrix and brown mottles from 38 to 90 cm. The hue index have a value of 0.7 in 30 cm surface layers but decreased to 0.11 in C horizons. The chroma index varies from 2.1 to 2.98 with depth. The Boritika soil (P4) on old floodplains

have dark grey to dark greyish brown matrix with chroma 1 or 2. This soil has 0.11 to 0.22 hue index and 2.25 to 2.70 chroma index with slight changes. The hue index has strong positive relation with Fe (0.43*) and Mn contents (0.42*) where as chroma index has a negative weak relation with Fe (-0.32) and Mn (-0.42*). This colour index had a non linear relationship with time of saturation¹⁹. Such kind of relations were reported in hydric soils of Brahmaputra valley by Bhaskar *et al.*¹³.

Particle size distribution and chemical properties :
The Kamalabari soil on active floodplains (P1) have 40 to 86% sand, 38 to 52% silt and 4.5 to 19% clay. The Adielengi soil (P2) on swamps shows gradational increase of sand from 14 to 96%, decrease of silt from 74 to 1.5%

and bulged distribution of clay from 11% in Ap horizon to 33 to 21% in Bw horizons and 5 to 9% in C horizons. Sonari- bari soil on channel fills (P3) have sand content of 1 to 46%, silt of 44 to 77% and duplex negative distribution of clay content of 9.5 to 34.5%. The cambic B horizons have more than 50% silt and 30.5% clay where as sand dominant in C horizons (78 to 93%). The high inflections of sand silt ratios with depth indicate textural contrast in soils of Brahmaputra as reported by many workers^{2,3,13,20}.

All soils are neutral to slightly alkaline except Kamalabari soil (P1) with moderately acid to neutral. The organic carbon varies from 9.7 g/kg (P2) to 19.5 g/kg (P3) in Ap horizons but decreased to 0.6 g/kg in C hori-

Table 1. Selected hydric soil characteristics under study area

Depth (cm)	Horizon	Colour index		Particle size (<2 mm) (%)			Sand/ silt	pH	OC (g/kg)	CEC cmol (+)kg ⁻¹	Elemental composition (g/kg)						
		C1	C2	Sand	Silt	Clay					K	Na	Ca	Fe	Mn	mg/kg	
																Cu	Zn
P1. Kamalabari series-Humaqueptic fluvaquents																	
0-19	Ap	0.32	9.1	42.7	38.3	19.0	1.11	5.9	12.2	12.6	3.4	1.2	2.7	30.1	0.37	28	109
19-39	AC	0.35	9.1	40.4	43.1	16.5	0.94	6.9	4.8	12.3	1.8	0.9	2.1	33.2	0.38	29	110
39-61	C1	0.22	9.45	40.4	52.6	7.0	0.77	7.0	1.9	10.2	1.8	0.9	3.2	32.0	0.51	27	117
61-89	C2	0.11	9.1	49.5	42.0	8.5	1.18	7.1	2.5	11.2	1.7	0.9	3.0	31.1	0.48	25	109
89-130	C3	0.11	9.1	86.0	9.5	4.5	9.1	7.2	0.8	7.61	1.3	0.9	3.2	23.1	0.40	14	116
P2. Adielengi-Typic Endoaqupts																	
0-13	Ap	0.11	2.31	14.7	74.3	11.0	0.19	7.1	9.7	11.1	8.8	2.5	8.5	38.3	0.64	39	77
13-34	Bw1	0.11	2.31	15.7	51.3	33.0	0.31	6.8	16.7	14.1	13.9	5.4	3.6	44.1	0.70	42	94
34-60	Bw2	0.55	2.70	22.4	56.6	21.0	0.40	7.0	5.8	12.5	9.4	2.8	4.1	41.5	0.81	44	81
60-98	C1	0.22	2.97	75.0	16.0	9.0	4.69	7.2	1.4	7.89	3.9	1.7	3.7	28.5	0.56	23	55
98-225	C2	0.11	2.86	96.3	1.5	5.0	74.1	7.2	1.4	3.48	2.1	1.5	2.6	14.6	0.26	5	30
P3. Sonaribari series-Fluventic Endoaqupts																	
0-13	Ap	0.70	2.42	1.6	63.9	34.5	0.03	6.7	19.5	17.5	10.7	2.65	5.90	45.1	0.65	50	104
13-31	B/A	0.70	2.42	1.0	78.5	20.5	0.01	7.7	10.2	14.2	10.6	2.80	10.4	45.5	0.76	48	101
31-38	Bw1	0.35	2.31	11.9	74.6	13.5	0.16	7.7	5.0	11.7	7.5	1.95	9.8	41.35	0.71	42	97
38-47	Bw2	0.70	2.70	46.3	44.2	9.5	1.05	7.9	3.9	10.9	5.7	1.60	10.3	37.25	0.62	33	84
47-56	Bw3	0.22	2.59	20.4	68.6	11.0	0.30	7.7	4.2	11.5	7.8	2.35	10.5	40.20	0.68	38	127
56-66	Bw4	0.22	2.99	8.1	75.4	16.5	0.11	7.8	6.2	12.6	7.1	1.90	8.95	41.65	0.75	42	105
66-90	C	0.11	2.59	14.7	73.3	12.0	0.20	7.6	6.4	10.2	7.3	1.85	9.60	43.10	0.71	44	90
P4. Boritika series-Fluvaquentic Endoaqupts																	
0-26	Ap	0.11	2.37	29.4	46.6	24	0.63	7.0	12.3	17.9	10.9	3.45	3.8	36.2	0.58	36	87
26-52	C1	0.11	2.37	77.5	16.5	6	4.69	7.5	1.6	11.9	4.2	2.00	4.45	23.4	0.36	18	53
52-64	2Bw1	0.11	2.7	13.3	52.2	34.5	0.25	7.2	11.0	19.6	8.9	2.35	3.00	36.5	0.42	44	88
64-79	2Bw2	0.22	2.26	17.1	53.4	29.5	0.33	7.3	4.3	20.0	8.0	2.50	3.15	38.9	0.43	49	90
79-113	C2	0.22	2.26	92.5	1.0	6.5	92.5	7.6	0.6	8.89	3.3	1.55	4.15	18.8	0.36	8	36

Foot note : C1 = hue index, C2 = chroma index, OC = organic carbon, CEC = cation exchange capacity.

zons (Table 1). These soils have low cation exchange capacity 3.5 cmol/kg in C horizons of P2 to 20 cmol/kg in 2Bw2 (P4) due to destruction of silicate clay during ferrollysis²¹ causing replacement of exchangeable bases by Fe²⁺ upon the onset of reduced conditions. Under oxidized conditions, iron gets precipitated and produces H⁺ that causes charge reduction and loss of Al³⁺ from octahedral layer. The cation exchange capacity is positively and significantly related with organic carbon (0.63**) and clay (0.86**) and expressed in regression equation as :

$$\bullet \text{CEC (cmol (p+) kg}^{-1}\text{)} = 0.853 (\text{organic carbon (g/kg)}) - 3.99$$

$$\bullet \text{CEC (cmol (p+) kg}^{-1}\text{)} = 2.15 (\text{clay \%}) - 10.35$$

Elemental composition : The elemental composition of hydric soils of Majuli island is presented in Table 1. The total K content shows gradational decrease in all soils with its weighted mean content of 1.85 g/kg in P1 and 6.47 g/kg in P4. The striking differences in distribution of Ca in P1 (weighted mean of 2.91 g/kg) and in P3 (9.32 g/kg) point out the susceptibility to leaching and rapid weathering of calcic minerals in soils²² whereas total Fe and Mn contents are low in soils on swamps (P2) and floodplains (P1 and P4) indicating loss of Fe and Mn through ground water flow and enriching gleyzation processes⁹ in the B horizons with Fe (40.2 g/kg P3 and 38.9 g/kg P4) and Mn (0.751 g/kg in 4 P3 and 0.81 g/kg in P2) at an observed redox potential of E_H, 170 mV¹⁹. The Cu content in Sonaribari series (P3) vary from 33 to 50

mg/kg with decreasing trend upto 47 cm but increases to 44 mg/kg at C horizons. The C horizons have Cu content less than 10 mg/kg in P2 and P4. The horizon wise distribution of Cu in Kamalabari series shows decreasing trend from 28 to 14 mg/kg but irregular in other soils. The Zn content is more than 100 mg/kg in P1 and in P3 but less in P2 and P4 with irregular depth trends. The lack of definite trends of Cu and Zn lends an indirect support of high degree of profile differentiation in soil profiles¹⁵. The clay mass in C horizons of swampy soils (P2) is 51 to 98 kg/m² but low in cambic horizons of channel fills (P3, 13.1 to 18.1 kg/m², Table 2). The mass of K, Ca, Cu and Zn is low with the pedogenic modification due to regular deposition of alluvium with striking profile distribution of K and Ca in P1 and P3. The enrichment of Fe and Mn mass in these soils shows positive relation with hue index (Fe r = 0.43* and Mn 0.42*) but negative with chroma index (Fe r = -0.32 and Mn -0.42*). The total Fe is positively and significantly related with clay (0.63**) and organic carbon (0.63**). Similar findings were reported in Indo-Gangetic plains of Punjab¹⁵ and in paddy growing soils of Brahmaputra valley¹.

The average linkage method was employed to work-out chemical affinity of soil horizons and derived four clusters. The cluster-1 includes 8 horizon sequences as cambic B horizons of Sonaribari (P3), Ap horizon of Adielengi (P2) have strong affinity with C1 horizons of Kamalabari (P1) and Boritika (P4) whereas in cluster-2 has strong affinity between C horizons of P1 and P3,

Table 2. Clay and elemental contents in the pedons expressed in terms of kg/m²

Depth (cm)	Horizon	kg/m ²							Bulk density (mg m ³)
		Clay	K	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn	
P1. Kamalabari series-Humaqueptic fluvaquents									
0-19	Ap	49.8	0.89	0.71	7.89	0.08	0.007	0.029	1.6
19-39	AC	44.2	0.48	0.56	8.89	0.10	0.007	0.029	1.7
39-61	C1	22.0	0.57	1.01	10.07	0.16	0.008	0.037	1.3
61-89	C2	34.3	0.68	1.21	12.54	0.19	0.011	0.044	1.4
89-130	C3	27.9	0.81	1.98	14.30	0.25	0.008	0.074	1.7
P2. Adielengi-Typic Endoaquepts									
0-13	Ap	21.3	1.70	1.65	7.42	0.12	0.007	0.015	1.49
13-34	Bw1	88.7	3.74	0.97	11.85	0.19	0.011	0.025	1.28
34-60	Bw2	71.5	3.20	1.40	14.13	0.28	0.015	0.028	1.31
60-98	C1	51.6	2.24	2.12	16.35	0.32	0.013	0.032	1.51
98-225	C2	97.8	4.11	5.10	28.55	0.51	0.009	0.059	1.54

Table-2 (contd.)

P3. Sonaribari series-Fluventic Endoauepts									
0-13	Ap	65.9	2.05	1.12	8.62	0.12	0.011	0.019	1.47
13-31	B/A	55.7	2.89	2.82	12.37	0.21	0.013	0.027	1.51
31-38	Bw1	13.1	0.73	0.95	4.02	0.07	0.004	0.008	1.39
38-47	Bw2	11.0	0.66	1.21	4.34	0.07	0.003	0.009	1.29
47-56	Bw3	13.2	0.93	1.26	4.81	0.08	0.005	0.015	1.33
56-66	Bw4	18.8	0.81	1.03	4.75	0.08	0.005	0.012	1.14
66-90	C	36.3	2.21	2.90	13.03	0.22	0.013	0.027	1.26
P4. Boritika series-Fluvaquentic Endoauepts									
0-26	Ap	82.4	3.74	1.30	12.42	0.19	0.012	0.029	1.32
26-52	C1	24.8	1.74	1.86	9.67	0.15	0.007	0.022	1.59
52-64	2Bw1	50.5	1.30	0.44	5.34	0.06	0.006	0.013	1.22
64-79	2Bw2	56.2	1.52	0.61	7.41	0.08	0.009	0.017	1.27
79-113	C2	23.4	1.19	1.51	6.78	0.13	0.003	0.013	1.06

cluster-3 with B and C horizons of P2 and Ap and AC horizons of P1 and in cluster-4 between B horizons of P2 and Ap horizons of P3 and P4. The cluster analysis shows the degree and kind of associations between the array of horizon sequences if arranged may clearly indicate the mode of deposition of alluvium in bringing out the pedogenic differentiation in soils. It is further evident from the mean mass of clay of in cluster-3 (52.1 kg/m²) with per cent of variation of 9.2% as against in cluster-4 with

mean clay of 81.26 kg/m² and coefficient of per cent of 15.82 (Table 3). Likewise, the mean mass of Ca (1.98 kg/m²), Fe (15.14 kg/m²) and Mn (0.26 kg/m²) shows more than 50 percent of variation in cluster-4.

Losses and gains of elements : The relative changes of P ratios compared with the C ratios with mass balances result in huge losses of elements under extreme reductive conditions in C horizons and impoverishment of elements (Table 4). Adielengi series on swamps (P2) has shown

Table 3. Cluster wise descriptive statistics of soil properties in hydric soils

Descriptive statistics	kg/m ²							Bulk density (mg m ³)
	Clay	K	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn	
Cluster-1								
Mean	18.45	1.04	1.31	6.48	0.11	0.005	0.016	1.32
SD	5.31	0.46	0.33	2.40	0.036	0.002	0.009	0.172
CV (%)	28.77	44.07	25.29	37.08	34.36	36.35	57.28	13.02
Cluster-2								
Mean	32.16	0.72	1.46	13.12	0.21	0.01	0.054	1.5
SD	3.69	0.075	0.44	1.01	0.034	0.0017	0.017	0.173
CV (%)	11.48	10.37	30.31	7.74	16.49	17.32	32.075	11.55
Cluster-3								
Mean	52.1	1.43	0.96	8.22	0.10	0.008	0.022	1.43
SD	4.83	0.82	0.92	2.34	0.054	0.0025	0.007	0.201734
CV (%)	9.27	57.18	95.60	28.48	53.66	29.52	32.39	14.12
Cluster-4								
Mean	81.26	3.36	1.98	15.14	0.26	0.011	0.032	1.38
SD	12.85	0.81	1.75	7.77	0.15	0.0021	0.015	0.11
CV (%)	15.82	23.90	88.62	51.42	58.87	18.88	48.71	8.25

Foot note : SD = standard deviation, CV = coefficient of variation.

Table 4. Per cent losses and gains of elements in hydric soils

Depth (cm)	Horizon	K	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn
P1. Kamalabari series-Humaqueptic fluvaquents							
0-19	Ap	-37.9	-79.8	-69.1	-81.62	-52.6	-78.3
19-39	AC	-62.1	82.1	-60.73	-74.1	-43.4	-74.9
39-61	C1	-10.6	-35.6	-10.7	-17.9	+24.31	-35.6
61-89	C2	-30.6	-50.4	-28.7	-36.44	-5.4	-51.4
Net gain/loss (%)		-35.32	-61.9	-42.3	-52.5	-19.3	-60.1
P2. Adielengi-Typic Endoaquepts							
0-13	Ap	+90.47	+49.32	+19.22	+11.7	+255.3	+16.74
13-34	Bw1	0	-78.9	-54.1	-59.3	+26.75	-52.7
34-60	Bw2	+7.14	-62.4	-43.2	-25.9	+07.6	-35.6
60-98	C1	+2.38	-20.8	+8.5	+19.4	+155.6	+2.0
Net gain/loss (%)		+24.94	-28.3	-19.4	-13.5	+136.4	-17.4
P3. Sonaribari series-Fluventic Endoaquepts							
0-13	Ap	-48.8	-78.6	-63.6	-68.3	-56.6	-61.3
13-31	B/A	-14.5	-36.6	-38.2	-37.3	-36.24	-34.9
31-38	Bw1	-8.4	-8.9	-14.4	-10.8	-15.0	-10.82
38-47	Bw2	-1.0	+37.3	+9.9	+10.6	-5.2	+12.6
47-56	Bw3	+16.4	+19.1	+1.5	+4.2	-6.1	+57.2
56-66	Bw4	-29.2	-31.8	-29.6	-23.1	-27.3	-11.0
Net gain/loss (%)		-14.3	-16.6	-22.4	-20.8	+24.4	-8.1
P4. Boritika series-Fluvaquentic Endoaquepts							
0-26	Ap	-12	-76.92	-47.75	-56.1	+20.9	-35.7
26-52	C1	+37	+15.38	+34.94	+17.64	+140.0	+58.91
52-64	2Bw1	-51	-86.6	-63.3	-70.6	+2.4	-53.9
64-79	2Bw2	-47	-83.1	-54.33	-73.5	+33.1	-46.1
Net gain/loss (%)		-18.13	-57.8	-32.6	-45.1	+41.0	-19.1

the enrichment of K and Cu throughout profile with net gain of 25% for K and 136% of Cu with slight loss of Ca (28%), Fe (19.4%), Mn (13.5%) and Zn (17.4%). In P3, little gains of K, Ca, Fe, Mn and Zn in Bw horizons at 38 to 56 cm are helpful to differentiate and identify the biserial depositions in soils on channel fills. Severe loss of K, Ca, Fe, Mn and Zn elements in soils on old floodplains (P4) is due to intense leaching and low amount of mass added to profiles. The little losses of elements in P2 and P3 shows the less period of saturation as compared to (reducing conditions < 40% of time) severe losses in P1 and P4 (> 90% of reducing time). This is in agreement of findings reported in wetland soils of Allagu region in south West Germany¹⁹. The enrichment of Fe and Mn in swampy areas indicates low breakdown of minerals and

leaching of cations under neutral environment⁹. It is interesting to note that the Ap horizons in P2 has shown net gains of all elements indicating enrichment of elements in young alluvium.

Conclusions

Four hydric soils on southern bank of Majuli river island were selected for geochemical interpretations in relation to morphology and particle size distribution. These soils have depleted matrix with hue 10YR, 2.5Y and 5Y, chroma less than 2, stratified textures, neutral to slightly alkaline reaction, low cation exchange capacity and poor exchangeable base status. These soils were placed in the subgroups of aquents and aquepts. The element to clay ratios in the soils show that the total Fe is closely related to chroma index and clay. The swampy soils (P2) show

severe losses of cations and enrichment of Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn in C horizons. The severe loss of K, Zn and Ca is of great concern in these paddy soils with historical low yields. The horizon wise mass data sets of elements and clay are used to derive 4 groups based on similarity. The cluster-4 has high values of K (3.36 kg/m²), Ca (1.98 kg/m²), Fe (15.14 kg/m²) and Mn (0.26 kg/m²) with high coefficient of variation (50%). The geochemical data sets were helpful to traceout the depositional episodes as evident from thickening of B horizons in old floodplain and swampy soil profiles and subsoil acidity with moderately low saturated hydraulic conductivity and continuous submergence that promotes potassium and Zn deficiency for rice production.

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